

AN OVERVIEW OF EMERGING TRENDS IN ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE

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Article Received on 30 October 2025,
Article Revised on 20 Nov. 2025,
Article Published on 01 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17744929>

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How to cite this Article: Amrata Suryawanshi^{1*}, Ashte Sarika², Ashte Monika², Jangave Samiksha², Jadhav Divya², Shaikh Saniya², Shinde Dipali². (2025). AN OVERVIEW OF EMERGING TRENDS IN ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(12), 632–641.

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ABSTRACT

ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE is a growing global health concern characterized by the ability of micro organism such as bacteria to withstand the effect of drug that once killed them or inhibited their growth the misuses and overuse of antibiotic in human medicine, agriculture, and animal husbandry have accelerated the emergence of resistant strains. mechanisms of resistance include enzymatic drug inactivation, alteration of target sites, reduced permeability, and active efflux of drugs. the spread of resistance genes through horizontal gene transfer poses a significant threat to infection control antibiotic resistance leads to longer hospital stays, increased medical costs, and higher mortality rates. addressing this challenge requires coordinated efforts, including rational antibiotic use, strengthened infection prevention, surveillance programs, public awareness, and the development of novel antimicrobials and alternative therapies. Without urgent action, the post antibiotics era could compromise the effectiveness of modern

medicine. Pathogenic microbial biofilm, a consortium of microbial cells protected by a self-produced polymer matrix, is considered a worldwide challenge due to the inherent antibiotic resistance conferred by its lifestyle. Living, as it does, in a community of microbial organisms in a clinical situation, makes it responsible for severe and dangerous cases of infection. Multidrug-resistant (MDR) bacteria have increased at an alarming rate over recent decades and cause serious problems. The emergence of resistant infections caused by these

bacteria has led to mortality and morbidity; consequently there is an urgent need to find solution for combating bacterial resistance.

KEYPOINTS: TYPES OF RESISTANCE, Origin of Antibiotic Resistance, Phylogenetics of Ancient Resistance, Gram-positive strains Gram-negative strains.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing magnitude of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in human pathogens poses a significant threat to public health worldwide. The lack of development of new antibiotics and rising resistance to last-resort antibiotics exacerbate the issue. The Need to Conserve Antibiotics With limited treatment options, conserving existing antibiotics is crucial. Natural antibiotics have existed for billions of years, providing a selective benefit for producing strains. Origins of Antibiotics and Resistance Antibiotics and antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) are ancient, with studies identifying ARGs in permafrost samples and isolated cave microbiomes staphylococcus aureus: A Formidable Therapeutic Challenge Introduction Staphylococcus aureus is a Gram-positive microbe that colonizes human skin and nares, causing invasive diseases such as skin and soft tissue infections, bacteremia, sepsis, and endocarditis. The emergence of methicillin-resistant strains presents a significant therapeutic challenge. Coagulase: A Key Virulence FactorS. Aureus isolates can form clots in human citrate-plasma or blood due to the secretion of coagulase (Coa). Coa binds prothrombin, altering its active site and enabling the cleavage of fibrinogen to fibrin. Structure and Function of Coagulase

The mature form of Coa consists of

1. N-terminal D1 and D2 domains, which associate with and activate prothrombin
2. A linker (L) domain connecting D12 and the repeat (R) region
3. The repeat region, comprised of tandem repeats of a 27-residue peptide that binds fibrinogen

Coagulase Typing and Sequence Variation Coagulase typing has identified 10 different serological Coa types. DNA sequencing revealed significant variation within coa sequences, particularly in the D12 domain. The variation of coa sequences may enable *S. aureus* to circumvent humoral immune responses. Coa may represent a protective antigen and should be analyzed for its possible use as a vaccine antigen Understanding the mechanisms of Coa-mediated virulence and sequence variation can inform the development of effective vaccines

against *S. aureus* infections.

TYPES OF RESISTANCE

Antibiotic resistance is a growing concern, and understanding its types is crucial for developing effective strategies to combat it.

1. Intrinsic Resistance

- Mediated by chromosomal genes
- Linked to physiological or anatomical characteristics of bacteria
- Natural resistance to certain antimicrobial groups or substances
- resistant to penicillin G due to cell wall complexity
- Example: 1. Gram-negative bacteria resistant to vancomycin- Linked to physiological or anatomical characteristics of bacteria

2. Gram-negative bacteria in due to cell wall structure

2. Acquired Resistance

- Develops through mutation or genetic changes
- Bacteria can obtain resistance to antimicrobials through:
 - Mutation
 - Gene transfer (horizontal gene transfer)
 - Other mechanisms (e.g., efflux pumps, enzyme production)
- Develops through genetic changes:
 - Mutation in chromosomal DNA
 - Acquisition of exogenous DNA

Staphylococcus aureus
Cause blood poisoning

Acinetobacter
Cause blood poisoning

Enterococcus faecalis
Cause blood poisoning and

Neisseria gonorrhoeae
Cause gonorrhoea

Haemophilus influenzae

Fig. 1: Different types of Bacteria.

Fig. 2: Antimicrobial Resistance Containment and Surveillance Human/Animal Infections and Antimicrobial Use.

The use of antimicrobial drugs is a critical aspect of managing human and animal infections.

Factors Influencing Antimicrobial Use

1. Disease burden and prevention
2. Diagnostics and quality diagnostic testing
3. Prescribers' behavior and appropriate treatment regimens
4. Consumer expectations and adherence
5. Consumer health education

Disease Prevention and Control

- Reducing infectious disease incidence and prevalence is key to containing AMR

- Effective treatment and prevention strategies include:
- Clean water and safe food
- Hospital infection control
- Community education
- Vaccine development and use

Diagnostics and Quality Diagnostic Testing

- Essential for evaluating and managing infectious diseases

Antimicrobial Drugs and Regulatory Framework

Antimicrobial drugs are pharmaceutical formulations used to treat infectious diseases targeting specific microorganisms.

Regulatory Framework

1. A national regulatory authority is necessary for effective AMR containment
2. Core functions include:
3. Pre-marketing evaluation and approval of drugs
4. Regulation of drug manufacture, importation, and distribution
5. Enforcement of prescription-only antimicrobial drugs
6. Independent drug information for prescribers

Drug Quality and Approval

- Ineffective regulation leads to inferior quality drugs
- Low-quality drugs contribute to resistance and poor treatment outcomes
- Quality assurance systems are essential for AMR containment

Origin of Antibiotic Resistance

History of Antibiotic Resistance

- Resistance to sulfonamides reported in the 1930
- Aminoglycoside-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* emerged within 6 years of roduction
- Methicillin resistance reported soon after introduction in 1961
- Fluoroquinolone resistance emerged in the 1980s
- Vancomycin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (VRSA) reported in 2002

Fig. 3: Graphical representation of onset of antibiotic resistance versus time to get antibiotic resistance.

History of Antibiotic Discovery and Resistance

The development of antibiotic resistance has been a persistent challenge since the introduction of the first effective antimicrobials, sulfonamides, in 1937.

Timeline of Antibiotic Discovery and Resistance

- Dark Ages: Preantibiotic era
- Primordial: Advent of chemotherapy via sulfonamides (1937)
- Golden Age: Discovery of most antibiotics used today
- Lean Years: Low point of new antibiotic discovery and development
- Pharmacologic: Understanding and improving antibiotic use
- Biochemical: Knowledge of biochemical actions and resistance mechanisms
- Target: Mode-of-action and genetic studies
- Genomic/HTS: Genome sequencing and high-throughput screening
- Disenchantment: Failure of genome-based methods, leading to discontinued discovery programs

FIG. 4: History of Antibiotic Resistance The Phylogenetics of Ancient Resistance.

The evolutionary history of antibiotic resistance determinants is complex and influenced by various factors, including gene gain, duplication, loss, and horizontal gene transfer.

- Evolution is rarely linear, making dating efforts challenging.
- Gene gain, duplication, loss, and horizontal gene transfer confound phylogenetic analysis.
- Different genes and gene clusters may have distinct evolutionary histories.
- Inferring accurate gene trees given a known species tree.
- Inferring accurate species trees given gene trees.
- Joint estimation of both species and gene and tree.

Antibiotic Inactivation by Gram-positive isolates

Enzymes that modify antibiotics are of particular interest as they most likely evolved in direct response to the emergence of specific antibiotics to block their activity in contrast to mechanisms such as efflux that often can target several classes of bioactive compounds of diverse chemical structure. Within the isolates, we detected no inactivation of aminoglycosides, the lincosamide clindamycin, or chloramphenicol; antibiotics where enzymatic inactivation is a prevalent resistance mechanism in surface bacteria. On the other hand, substantial inactivation (22–62% of strains) was seen for β -lactams (the penicillins ampicillin, piperacillin and the cephalosporin cephalexin), which is primarily caused by the hydrolysis of β -lactam ring by β -lactamases. Enzymatic inactivation was detected for macrolide antibiotics in four strains: three isolates of *Streptomyces* spp. and one of *Brachybacterium paraconglomeratum*. These strains inactivated both the natural product

erythromycin and its 3rd generation semi-synthetic derivative telithromycin. Inactivation by the *Streptomyces* isolates yielded a product with a mass increase of 162, consistent with mono-glycosylation of the antibiotic. Inactive macrolide antibiotics from *B. paraconglomeratum* extracts on the other hand revealed a mass increase of 80, indicative of inactivation by phosphorylation. The lipopeptide daptomycin is the newest class of antibiotic approved for clinical use. Three *Streptomyces* strains were found to be highly resistant to daptomycin (MIC\$256 mg/ml) and inactivated the antibiotic through hydrolysis as assessed by LC/ MS (m/z increase of 18 g/mol). This result is consistent with the high level of daptomycin inactivation in surface *Streptomyces* where this is a constitutively expressed activity. Additionally, four isolates of *Paenibacillus lautus* completely inactivated daptomycin when grown at sub-MIC concentration of the antibiotic. Daptomycin inactivation has not been previously reported in low G+C bacteria (Firmicutes bacteria). Purification of the inactive product followed by MS/MS analysis revealed hydrolytic cleavage of the ester bond between the threonine and kynurenine residues resulting in ring-opening inactivation. The inactivation of daptomycin was highly sensitive to inhibition by EDTA, but not significantly by Ser esterase/protease inhibitors consistent with the possible involvement of a metallo-esterase. This contrasts with our recent analysis of *Streptomyces* daptomycin esterases, which appear to use canonical Ser catalytic triad chemistry to inactivate the antibiotic. Furthermore, unlike inactivation by *Streptomyces*, which appears to be constitutively expressed, the production of the inactivating activity in *P. lautus* was inducible by exposure to daptomycin. To explore if this activity was unique to the cave isolate, we obtained a surface strain of *P. lautus* (ATCC 43898) and observed similar results in enzymatic inactivation and antibiotic-associated induction of activity.

Antibiotic Inactivation by Gram-negative isolates

We observed little enzyme-mediated antibiotic inactivation in Gram-negative isolates suggesting that there are other molecular mechanisms of resistance at play such as efflux, target modification, or barriers to entry. Three strains belonging to the genera *Agrobacterium* and *Ochrobactrum* displayed chloramphenicol inactivation, which we determined by LC/MS to be the modification by acetylation a well-established resistance mechanism both in Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria.

Fig. 5: Resistance levels of Lechuguilla cave bacteria at 20 mg/ml against various antibiotics: (top) Gram-positive strains (bottom) Gram-negative strains.

CONCLUSION

Antibiotic resistance has emerged as one of the most serious global health threats, driven largely by misuse and overuse of antimicrobial agents. Without urgent action, common infections may once again become difficult or impossible to treat. Strengthening antimicrobial stewardship, promoting responsible antibiotic use, and improving surveillance are essential to slow the spread of resistance. A coordinated effort from healthcare professionals, policymakers, industries, and the public is crucial to safeguard the effectiveness of antibiotics for future generations. Antibiotic resistance represents a rapidly escalating challenge that threatens modern healthcare and global public health systems. The rise of resistant pathogens is fueled by inappropriate antibiotic use in humans, agriculture, and inadequate infection-control measures. If unaddressed, this crisis may lead to prolonged illnesses, higher healthcare costs, and increased mortality. Therefore, comprehensive strategies such as antimicrobial stewardship programs, enhanced diagnostics, stricter regulations on antibiotic use, and continuous public awareness are critical. Research and

development of novel antibiotics, vaccines, and alternative therapies must be prioritized to stay ahead of resistant organisms. Ultimately, combating antibiotic resistance requires a sustained, collaborative effort across healthcare providers, researchers, policymakers, and communities to preserve the life-saving power of antibiotics.

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